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A STUDY OF THE LEARNING PROBLEMS OF UNDERGRADUATE INDUSTRIAL DESIGN STUDENTS IN STUDIO COURSES

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to explore the learning problems of undergraduate industrial design students in studio courses. A questionnaire consisting of both closed and open questions was designed to collect data. The results of the survey illustrated that 1) the students regarded concept generation the most difficult task; 2) the major problems that students experienced were organizing and structuring design documentation, physical model making for design presentation, and selection of the design direction in the design research phase; 3) these main problems were related to personal issues. The results can serve as a reference point for future research and design education.

Keywords: industrial design, learning problems, design studio.

INTRODUCTION

The essential feature of design education is “learning by doing”. Students learn design knowledge and skill through working on real design problems. Based on this feature of design education, the problems that students experience in the learning process may be different than in other domains.

This study is part of a research project to explore learning problems and resources in industrial design education. The purpose of this study is to investigate the learning problems that undergraduate industrial design students experience in a studio course. The results could provide an increased understanding of students’ learning processes.

LITERATURE REVIEW

PROFESSIONAL DESIGN LEARNING

Learning is the act or process of developing skill or knowledge (Arsham, 2002). Design is generally considered to involve abductive reasoning, which addresses ill-defined problems and uses a construction process to solve them (Zimring & Latch Craig, 2001). Design knowledge is difficult to understand or to describe. It must be understood with reference to the problem context. It cannot be delivered by a traditional lecture pedagogy. The most commonly used approach is “learning by doing,” exemplified by the apprentice system, and therefore design learning emphasizes working with actual problems to acquire professional knowledge and techniques (Schön, 1987). Students need to acquire advanced knowledge through working with design problems in the real world. In the learning process, a teacher demonstrates and leads students to engage with a real design problem. Students try to observe, to understand, and to grasp the various methods and techniques through the process, to cultivate their observation and decision-making capabilities, to explore their own talents, and finally to develop their own procedure and style of design. Therefore, the design process can be considered as a social process in which the result is constructed using various kinds of knowledge (Bucciarelli, 2001). The principal and most important teaching method in design education is the studio (Reimer & Douglas, 2003; Schön, 1987), especially in architectural and industrial design. The main distinguishing features of studio pedagogy are the learning of procedures and methods of design and the accumulation of

experience through the process of solving actual design problems. The emphases are on the presentation of design concepts and ideas, the critique and communication involved in the design process, and the learning of advanced design knowledge through reflection on design problems. Students go through the design procedure to solve real or simulated design problems (Attoe & Mugerauer, 1991; Budd, Vanka, & Runton, 1999; Forgber & Russell, 1999). In the studio, students are exposed to a number of learning experiences, focusing on two key aspects. The first is learning how to design by engagement with a design process or a suite of possible design methodologies. The second is to reveal knowledge about concepts, situations, or both through the act of designing (Smith, Hedley, & Molloy, 2009).

The design studio is the heart of most industrial design and architecture curricula. There are several factors associated with a successful design studio.

The “studio teaching project”

(<http://www.studioteaching.org>) supported by the Australian Learning & Teaching Council proposed that there are several key qualities or characteristics that play important roles in a typical successful studio program: 1) People: lecturers, tutors, technicians, members of various professional communities, and student peers; 2) Facilities and Resources: space, equipment, technologies, and materials; 3) Projects: areas of study, tasks, and problems to be solved, especially those related to industry and the profession; and 4) Time: the proportion of course time provided for studio work and hours of access to facilities. Attoe & Mugerauer (1991) also discussed the factors associated with teaching excellence in design studios and mentioned three considerations: 1) the teacher as self (aspects of the teacher’s own life that contributes to good teaching); 2) personal style (the way the teacher behaves); and 3) course format and implementation.

LEARNING PROBLEMS IN DESIGN STUDIO

The design studio is the place to practice and to integrate the knowledge and skills that are learned from the surrounding courses. There are people involved with the design learning process, for example, classmates, instructors, technicians, and other experts. It also needs environments and

settings to support the design learning process, such as personal working space, workshops, a library, etc. Learning the process of design is similar to designing. Both events involve spending certain periods of time thinking through the process and attempting to create some interesting results. Learners often have to explore and discover their own paths to gain knowledge and skills (Chang & Huang, 2002). Students must face a number of problems as they work through their design process.

LEARNING PROBLEMS

The issues involved in students’ learning problems or difficulties are complex and depend on a range of factors, including course organization and development, the subject or topic being taught, teaching style, and students’ expectations (Chang, Hsiao, Yeh, & Wu, 2000; Pirrie, Hamilton, & Wilson, 1999).

Design students face certain learning problems and difficulties as they explore the design problem space. Yang, You, & Chen (2005) investigated the difficulties faced by industrial design students and their career guidance needs. Focus group interviews was used to collect data. The participants included freshmen, seniors, graduates of senior high schools, and vocational high schools, with or without a design background. The problems that students encountered were: 1) high learning pressure and frustration; 2) heavy workload, which deprived them of extracurricular activities and leisure; 3) competition among classmates, which had an influence on peer relationships; 4) high costs of materials, resulting in financial pressure; 5) feelings of uncertainty and worries about the future; and 6) insufficient interaction between faculty and students. Chen (2009) investigated the problems that undergraduate industrial design students faced in studio courses. The most difficult tasks according to students were concept generation (66.7%), design presentation (64.8%), and design decision (50.0%). The problems in design tasks according to student responses were categorized as shown in Figure 1. Chen & Tang (2011) explored learning problems in the design studio using a questionnaire survey. All the problems about which students responded were coded and divided into three categories: 1) personal (89.6%); 2) resources (6.1%); and 3) interaction and

communication (4.3%). The personal problems included capabilities, thinking, techniques and skills, experiences, personality, knowledge, and other issues. The resource problems included money (cost), time, technical support, equipment, and related courses. The interaction and communication problems occurred with both instructors and peers. The top three major problems in the design research task were personal thinking (49.3%), capabilities (14.3%), and experiences (8.5%); in concept generation, they were personal thinking (53.7%), capabilities (10.1%), and experiences (9.4%); in design decision, they were personal capabilities (31.0%), thinking (23.1%), and interaction and communication with instructors (9.9%); in design presentation, they were personal capability (38.2%), techniques and skills (30.3%), and personality (6.8%). The personal factors of capabilities (60.2%), thinking

(9.7%), and techniques and skills (7.1%) were the top three problems in the design documentation task. The main method for design education is the studio, where students learn design knowledge through the design process by working on real design problems. Learning design is similar to designing. Students need to solve many learning problems as well as design problems. It is worthwhile to explore and study the various design learning problems encountered to develop solutions to solve them.

METHOD

This study primarily involved a survey, which consisted of a questionnaire about the learning problems that undergraduate industrial design students experienced in their studio course, and the collection of personal background information.

Figure 1. Learning problems encountered by undergraduate industrial design students in studio courses (translated by authors) (Chen, 2009).

SUBJECTS

The participants in this study were 189 undergraduate industrial design students from three different Universities in Taiwan. The subjects' attributes are shown in Table 1.

	School			Gender		Year	
	U1	U2	U3	Female	Male	2nd	3rd
Frequency	42	127	20	116	73	88	101
Percentage	22.2	76.2	10.0	61.4	38.6	46.6	53.4

Table 1. Subject numbers and percentages by school, gender, and year.

INSTRUMENT

A questionnaire was designed to collect the data. There are three parts in the questionnaire: 1) closed-type questions in which students had to choose the most difficult design tasks in their opinion; 2) open-type questions which provided students an opportunity to identify the problems that they had experienced in each design task; 3) personal background information. The design task categories used in the questionnaire include design research, concept generation, design decision, design presentation, and design documentation.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

The survey was conducted in the middle of the semester, using the questionnaire designed by the authors. The time available to answer the questionnaire was approximately 25 minutes. Both qualitative and quantitative data analyses were performed. The answers to the open-type questions were coded using the schemes proposed by Chen (2009) and Chen & Tang (2011) modified for this purpose. Figure 2 presents the coding system based on the task attributes of learning problems, and Figure 3 presents the coding system that based on related issues. This multiple coding strategy was used to avoid losing important information. The quantitative analysis of the questionnaire and coded data were then conducted using the SPSS software.

Figure 2. The task-based coding system (TBCS).

Figure 3. The issue-based coding system (IBCS).

RESULTS

BASIC INFORMATION

The students spent on average 30.63 (SD = 19.48) hours per week on their design learning projects. They slept 5.47 (SD = 1.04) hours and spent 4.85 (SD = 2.50) hours surfing on the Internet every day on average.

THE MOST DIFFICULT DESIGN TASKS

Table 2 shows the percentage of design tasks that students regarded as the most difficult by year, gender, and school. The results show that the top three difficulties design tasks that students identified were *concept generation* (82.5%), *design presentation* (40.7%), and *design research* (34.4%).

Task	Year		Gender		School			Total
	2	3	F	M	U1	U2	U3	
Design Research	34.1	34.7	32.8	37.0	21.4	37.8	40.0	34.4
Concept Generation	89.8	76.2	81.9	83.6	73.8	85.8	80.0	82.5
Design Decision	34.1	28.7	33.6	27.4	50.0	25.2	30.0	31.2
Design Presentation	39.8	41.6	40.5	41.1	54.8	36.2	40.0	40.7
Design Documentation	15.9	7.9	14.7	6.8	2.4	15.0	10.0	11.6
X ²		2.676		3.052			16.361	
df		4		4			8	
P Value		0.613		0.549			0.037*	

Table 2. Percentage ratings of the most difficult design tasks as identified by students by year, gender, and school; results of chi-square tests (percentage = number of responses / number of subjects, * p < 0.05).

The chi-square tests were conducted to test the homogeneity of proportions between years, genders, and schools. The result indicates a significant difference among schools ($X^2 = 16.361$, $df = 8$, $p = 0.037 < 0.05$). The top three tasks that U1 students regarded as the most difficult problems were *concept generation* (73.8%), *design presentation* (54.8%), and *design decision* (50.0%); for U2 students, they were *concept generation* (85.8%), *design research* (37.8%), and *design presentation* (36.2%); for U3 students, they were *concept generation* (80%), *design research* (40%), and *design presentation* (40%). The U1 students seemed to face more difficulties than U2 and U3 students, especially in the *design decision* task. U2 and U3 students seemed to have more difficulties in *design research* and *design documentation*. However, no significant difference by gender ($X^2 = 3.052$, $df = 4$, $p = 0.549 > 0.05$) or by year ($X^2 = 2.676$, $df = 4$, $p = 0.613 > 0.05$) was found.

LEARNING PROBLEMS

The frequencies and percentages of the problems that students identified were coded using the TBCS, and the results are shown in Table 3. The top three major problems in the *design research* task were selection of the design direction (85.71%), understanding of the design theme (64.55%), and target setting (22.75%); in *concept generation*, they were inspiration (52.91%), lateral thinking (37.57%), and skill in concept presentation (29.10%); in *design decision*, they were decision-making ability (66.14%), quality of concept (66.14%), and decision conflict (46.56%); in *design presentation*, they were physical modeling (87.83%), graphic presentation (74.60%), and oral presentation (71.96%); and in the *design documentation* task, they were organization and structure (121.16%), layout and editing (52.91%), and data collection (45.50%).

Task	Problem	Freq.	%
Design Research	Data collection	41	21.69
	Data analysis	17	8.99
	Data Present	8	4.23
	Understanding of the design theme	122	64.55
	Selection of the design direction.	162	85.71
	Target setting	43	22.75
	Other	199	105.29
Concept Generation	Lateral thinking	71	37.57
	Vertical thinking	15	7.94
	Skill of concept present	55	29.10
	Inspiration	100	52.91
	Form & style	26	13.76
	Reference information	5	2.65
	Other	314	166.14
Design Decision	Decision-making ability	125	66.14
	Quantity of concept	12	6.35
	Quality of concept	125	66.14
	Criteria for evaluation	36	19.05
	Evaluation method	3	1.59
	Decision conflict	88	46.56
	Other	180	95.24
Design Presentation	Digital modeling	30	15.87
	Physical modeling	166	87.83
	Graphic	141	74.60
	Oral	136	71.96
	Organization & logic	62	32.80
	Cost	30	15.87
	Other	39	20.63
Design Documentation	Data collection	86	45.50
	Organization & structure	229	121.16
	Layout & editing	100	52.91
	Time	9	4.76
	Money	8	4.23
	Other	136	71.96

Table 3. Frequencies and percentages of problems that students faced in each design task (percentage = number of responses / number of subjects).

The problems that most students experienced were organization and structure (121.16%) of *design documentation*, physical model-making (87.83%) in the *design presentation* task, and selection of the design direction (85.71%) in the *design research* task, leaving out certain problems that were not coded using the coding scheme.

The students regard *concept generation* as the most difficult task in the entire design process. The problems that they frequently experienced in this task were inspiration (57.67%) and lateral thinking (47.09%).

To identify any differences due to gender, year, or schools on each problems, a z-test (two-sided) was conducted to compare the proportions of the variables with a significance level of 0.05. Table 4 presents a summary of the z-test results. There were no significant differences due to gender or year in the responses to the previous section that provided the students' subjective responses to closed-type questions on the most difficult design tasks. However, there were some significant differences by gender and year in the students' answers to the open-type questions. The results demonstrated that male students experienced more problems with data collection (Male = 32.88%, Female = 14.66%) in the *design research* task and produced more concepts (Male = 10.96%, Female = 3.44%) in the *design decision* task than female students. The female students experienced more problems in understanding the design theme (Female = 73.28%, Male = 50.68%) in the *design research* task, in decision-making (Female = 75.86%, Male = 50.68%) in the *design decision* task, and with oral presentation skills (Female = 81.90%, Male = 56.16%) in the *design presentation* task than male students.

The third-year students experienced more problems with data collection (3rd = 35.64%, 2nd = 5.68%) in the *design research* task and encountered more materials-cost problems (3rd = 24.75%, 2nd = 5.68%) in the *design presentation* task than second-year students. The second-year students experienced more problems with concept presentation skills (2nd = 38.63%, 3rd = 20.79%) in the *concept generation* task than third-year students.

There were also some significant differences between schools. For example, U1 students experienced more problems with data collection and

analysis than U2 students in the *design research* task. U1 students also had more problems with lateral thinking than U2 and U3 students in the *concept generation* task.

Task	Problem	Gender	Year	School
DR	Data collection	M>F	3>2	(1=3)>2
	Data analysis	M>F		(1=3)≥(3=2)
	Data Present			
	Understanding of the design theme	F>M		
	Selection of the design direction.			
	Target setting			
	Other			(2=3)≥(3=1)
CG	Lateral thinking			1>(2=3)
	Vertical thinking			
	Skill of concept present		2>3	
	Inspiration			
	Form & style			
	Reference information			
	Other		3>2	
DDec	Decision-making ability	F>M		
	Quantity of concept	M>F		
	Quality of concept			
	Criteria for evaluation			
	Evaluation method			
	Decision conflict			
	Other	M>F		
DP	Digital modeling			
	Physical modeling			
	Graphic			
	Oral	F>M		
	Organization & logic			
	Cost		3>2	
	Other			(1=3)≥(3=2)
DDoc	Data collection			1>(2=3)
	Organization & structure		2>3	
	Layout & editing			
	Time			
	Money			(1=3)≥(3=2)
	Other			

Table 4. Test of differences by gender, year, and school. Results are based on two-sided tests with significance level 0.05. For each significant pair, the key of the category with the smaller column proportion appears under the category with the larger column proportion. (DR: Design Research, CG: Concept Generation, DDec: Design Decision, DP: Design Presentation, DDoc: Design Documentation)

Phase	Problem	Related Issues		
		Per.	Res.	Int.
DR	Data collection	85.37	14.63	0.00
	Data analysis	85.00	15.00	0.00
	Data Present	100.00	0.00	0.00
	Understanding of the design theme	95.90	0.00	4.10
	Selection of the design direction.	98.77	0.00	1.23
	Target setting	100.00	0.00	0.00
	Other	87.94	7.54	4.52
CG	Lateral thinking	98.59	0.00	1.41
	Vertical thinking	100.00	0.00	0.00
	Skill of concept present	98.21	0.00	1.79
	Inspiration	100.00	0.00	0.00
	Form & style	100.00	0.00	0.00
	Reference information	40.00	60.00	0.00
	Other	87.90	3.82	8.28
DDec	Decision-making capability	100.00	0.00	0.00
	Quantity of concept	100.00	0.00	0.00
	Quality of concept	99.20	0.00	0.80
	Criteria for evaluation	100.00	0.00	0.00
	Evaluation method	100.00	0.00	0.00
	Decision conflict	25.00	1.14	73.86
	Other	85.56	10.00	4.44
DP	Digital modeling	85.71	14.29	0.00
	Physical modeling	87.35	12.65	0.00
	Graphic	98.58	1.42	0.00
	Oral	98.53	0.00	1.47
	Organization & logic	93.94	6.06	0.00
	Cost	16.67	83.33	0.00
	Other	84.21	15.79	0.00
DDoc	Data collection	91.86	8.14	0.00
	Organization & structure	100.00	0.00	0.00
	Layout & editing	98.00	2.00	0.00
	Time	33.33	66.67	0.00
	Money	12.50	87.50	0.00
	Other	82.61	12.32	5.07

Table 5. Percentages of related issues by problem that students faced in each design task. (DR: Design Research, CG: Concept Generation, DDec: Design Decision, DP: Design Presentation, DDoc: Design Documentation, Per: Personal, Res: Resources, Int: Interaction)

The frequencies and percentages of the related issues that students identified were coded using the IBCS, and the results are shown in Table 5. Most of these problems were related to *personal* issues. There were some problems related to *resources* issues, such as data collection (14.63%) and data analysis (15.00%) in the *design research* task; finding reference information (60.00%) in the *concept*

generation task; dealing with decision conflict (1.14%) in the *design decision* task; materials cost (83.33%), digital modeling (14.29%), physical modeling (12.65%), and organization and logic (6.06%) in *design presentation*; and money (87.50%), time (66.67%), data collection (8.14%), and layout and editing (2.00%) in the *design documentation* task. Problems related to *interaction* issues included understanding the design theme (4.10%), selection of the design direction (1.23%) in *design research* task; concept presentation skills (1.79%) and lateral thinking (1.41%) in *concept generation*; resolving decision conflict (73.86%) and quality of concepts (0.80%) in *design decision*; and oral presentation skills (1.47%) in the *design presentation* task.

CONCLUSIONS

Learning design is similar to designing. The purpose of this study was to investigate the learning problems of undergraduate industrial design students in a studio course.

The results indicate that 1) the students regarded *concept generation* (82.5%) as the most difficult task; 2) the major problems students experienced included the organization and structure of the *design documentation* (121.16%), physical model-making for *design presentation* (87.83%), and selection of the design direction in the *design research* phase (85.71%); 3) the main problems were related to *personal* issues.

Professional design learning is a complex challenge. This study is exploratory, and therefore its findings are not conclusive. Future research will aim to provide more detailed insights into learning problems and to explore the learning resources that students use to solve problems.

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